

An optimization approach for fractional reaction-diffusion equations with nonlocal boundary conditions

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we present an optimization approach for solving fractional reaction-diffusion equations with nonlocal boundary conditions. To receive the desired goal, we applied a modified operational matrix of integration and an operational matrix of fractional derivative. At last, to demonstrate the accuracy of the method, we present an example.

Keywords: Lucas polynomials, Operational matrix, Optimization method, Fractional reaction-diffusion equation

AMS Mathematics Subject Classification [2010]: 65D99, 35R11, 65N35

1. Introduction

This type of equation has attracted the attention of many researchers. So that several methods have been proposed to solve these equations. For more familiarity with this issue, see references [1–4]. Throughout this paper, we utilize the Lucas polynomials [5, 6] and their properties for solving the proposed problem.

2. Lucas polynomials

This section introduces the Lucas polynomials and their properties. The explicit formula of Lucas polynomials is defined as follows [5, 6]:

$$(1) \quad L_0(x) = 2, \quad L_m(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \frac{m}{m-k} \binom{m-k}{k} x^{m-2k}.$$

Also, the approximation of an arbitrary function $f(x)$ by Lucas polynomials on the interval $[0, 1]$ is as follows:

$$f(x) \simeq \sum_{i=0}^{M_1} c_i L_i(x) = C^T L(x),$$

Here, the components of the coefficient vector are obtained by using regular grid points.

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3. Operational matrix of fractional derivative

This section presents the method of obtaining an operational matrix of fractional derivative. Let

$$(2) \quad D_t^\gamma L(t) \simeq t^{-\gamma} \Lambda_\gamma L(t), \quad q-1 < \gamma \leq q, \quad q \in N,$$

where Λ_γ denotes operational matrix of fractional derivative. According to the Lucas polynomials definition in Eq. (1) and Caputo fractional derivative, we get

$$(3) \quad \begin{aligned} D_t^\gamma L_m(t) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \frac{m}{m-k} \binom{m-k}{k} D_t^\gamma (t^{m-2k}) \\ &= \sum_{k=\lceil \frac{m-\gamma}{2} \rceil}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \frac{m}{m-k} \binom{m-k}{k} \frac{\Gamma(m-2k+1)}{\Gamma(m-2k+1-\gamma)} t^{m-2k-\gamma} \\ &\simeq t^{-\gamma} \sum_{k=\lceil \frac{m-\gamma}{2} \rceil}^{\lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \rfloor} \xi_{m,k}^\gamma t^{m-2k} = t^{-\gamma} \sum_{k=\lceil \frac{m-\gamma}{2} \rceil}^{\lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \rfloor} \xi_{m,k}^\gamma \left(\sum_{n=0}^{M_1} a_n L_n(t) \right) \\ &= t^{-\gamma} \sum_{n=0}^{M_1} \lambda_{m,k,n}^\gamma L_n(t), \quad \lambda_{m,n,k}^\gamma = \sum_{k=\lceil \frac{m-\gamma}{2} \rceil}^{\lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \rfloor} \xi_{m,k}^\gamma a_n. \end{aligned}$$

It should be noted that in the above process, we approximated t^{m-2k} with respect to the Lucas polynomials vector. Therefore, we have

$$\Lambda_\gamma = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{0,k,0}^\gamma & \lambda_{0,k,1}^\gamma & \cdots & \lambda_{0,k,M_1}^\gamma \\ \lambda_{1,k,0}^\gamma & \lambda_{1,k,1}^\gamma & \cdots & \lambda_{1,k,M_1}^\gamma \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ \lambda_{M_1,k,0}^\gamma & \lambda_{M_1,k,1}^\gamma & \cdots & \lambda_{M_1,k,M_1}^\gamma \end{bmatrix}.$$

4. Method of solution

In this section, we discussed the numerical solution of the following equation [3]:

$$(4) \quad D_t^\gamma u(x, t) - \frac{\partial^2 u(x, t)}{\partial x^2} = F(x, t), \quad (x, t) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1], \quad 0 < \gamma \leq 1,$$

subject to the mixed nonlocal supplementary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, 0) &= f(x), \\ u(0, t) &= \int_0^1 k_0(x) u(x, t) dx + \varphi_0(t), \quad u(1, t) = \int_0^1 k_1(x) u(x, t) dx + \varphi_1(t). \end{aligned}$$

To receive the proposed goal, we consider

$$(5) \quad u(x, t) \simeq L^T(x) U L(t), \quad U = [u_{ij}], \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, M_1, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M_2.$$

By considering the operational matrix of derivative and Eq. (5), we have

$$(6) \quad \frac{\partial^2 u(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \simeq x^{-2} L^T(x) \Lambda_2^T U L(t), \quad D_t^\gamma u(x, t) \simeq t^{-\gamma} L^T(x) U \Lambda_\gamma L(t).$$

By substituting the above approximation in Eq. (4), we obtain

$$(7) \quad \Psi(x, t) = t^{-\gamma} L^T(x) U \Lambda_\gamma L(t) - x^{-2} L^T(x) \Lambda_2^T U L(t) - F(x, t).$$

Next, due to the conditions and Eq. (5), we have

$$(8) \quad \begin{aligned} \Phi_1(x) &= L^T(x)UL(0) - f(x), \\ \Phi_2(t) &= L^T(0)UL(t) - \int_0^1 k_0(x)L^T(x)UL(t)dx - \varphi_0(t), \\ \Phi_3(t) &= L^T(1)UL(t) - \int_0^1 k_1(x)L^T(x)UL(t)dx - \varphi_1(t). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, from Eqs. (7) and (8) the optimization problem is achieved as follows:

$$(9) \quad \begin{aligned} \text{Min } \Delta(U) &= \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \Psi^2(x, t)dxdt, \\ \text{subject to} & \\ &\Phi_1(x) = 0, \quad \Phi_2(t) = 0, \quad \Phi_3(t) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

To obtain the optimal value of coefficient matrix elements, we define

$$(10) \quad \begin{aligned} \Delta^*(U, L_1, L_2, L_3) &= \Delta(U) + L_1^T \Phi_1 + L_2^T \Phi_2 + L_3^T \Phi_3, \\ L_1 &= [l_0^1, l_1^1, \dots, l_{M_1}^1]^T, \quad L_2 = [l_0^2, l_1^2, \dots, l_{M_2}^2]^T, \quad L_3 = [l_0^3, l_1^3, \dots, l_{M_2}^3]^T, \\ \Phi_1 &= [\Phi_1(x_i)]_{(M_1+1) \times 1}^T, \quad \Phi_2 = [\Phi_2(t_j)]_{(M_2+1) \times 1}^T, \quad \Phi_3 = [\Phi_3(t_j)]_{(M_2+1) \times 1}^T. \end{aligned}$$

At last, to get the approximate solutions of the problem, we consider the following conditions:

$$\frac{\partial \Delta^*(U, L_1, L_2, L_3)}{\partial U} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \Delta^*(U, L_1, L_2, L_3)}{\partial L_k} = 0, \quad k = 1, 2, 3.$$

5. Illustrative example

In this section, we implement the presented method for solving an example. It is worth noting that the computations were performed on a personal computer and the codes were written in MATLAB 2016.

EXAMPLE 5.1. Consider the following fractional reaction-diffusion equations with non-local boundary conditions [1, 2]:

$$D_t^\gamma u(x, t) - \frac{\partial^2 u(x, t)}{\partial x^2} = -\exp(-t) \left(x(x-1) + \frac{\delta}{6(1+\delta)+2} \right), \quad (x, t) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1],$$

with the mixed nonlocal supplementary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, 0) &= x(x-1) + \frac{\delta}{6(1+\delta)+2}, \\ u(0, t) &= \int_0^1 -\delta u(x, t)dx, \quad u(1, t) = \int_0^1 -\delta u(x, t)dx, \end{aligned}$$

The exact solution for $\gamma = 1$ is $u(x, t) = -\exp(-t) \left(x(x-1) + \frac{\delta}{6(1+\delta)} \right)$. The results are illustrated in Tables 1 and 2. Table 2 shows that the present method is more accurate than methods in [1, 2].

TABLE 1. The absolute error of the approximate solution for diverse choices of M_2 with $\gamma = 1$, $\delta = 0.0144$, $t = 0.5$ and $M_1 = 2$ of Example 5.1.

x	Present method		Operational matrix method [1]	Tau method [2]
	$M_2 = 4$	$M_2 = 8$	$n = 10$	$n = 8$
0.1	5.1302×10^{-8}	3.3351×10^{-13}	1.029×10^{-12}	5.4252×10^{-13}
0.2	9.2281×10^{-8}	6.0000×10^{-13}	1.851×10^{-12}	9.3545×10^{-13}
0.3	1.2155×10^{-7}	7.9034×10^{-13}	2.438×10^{-12}	1.1939×10^{-12}
0.4	1.3911×10^{-7}	9.0454×10^{-13}	2.790×10^{-12}	1.3398×10^{-12}
0.5	1.4496×10^{-7}	9.4260×10^{-13}	2.908×10^{-12}	1.3869×10^{-12}
0.6	1.3911×10^{-7}	9.0451×10^{-13}	2.790×10^{-12}	1.3398×10^{-12}
0.7	1.2155×10^{-7}	7.9027×10^{-13}	2.438×10^{-12}	1.1939×10^{-12}
0.8	9.2281×10^{-8}	5.9990×10^{-13}	1.851×10^{-12}	9.3545×10^{-13}
0.9	5.1302×10^{-8}	3.3338×10^{-13}	1.029×10^{-12}	5.4252×10^{-13}
1.0	1.3850×10^{-9}	9.2847×10^{-15}	2.772×10^{-14}	1.3687×10^{-14}

TABLE 2. The approximate solution for diverse choices of γ with $M_1 = 2$, $M_2 = 4$ and $\delta = 0.0144$ of Example 5.1.

$x = t$	$\gamma = 0.6$	$\gamma = 0.7$	$\gamma = 0.8$	$\gamma = 0.9$	Exact solution
0.1	7.6846×10^{-2}	7.7309×10^{-2}	7.7845×10^{-2}	7.8489×10^{-2}	7.9294×10^{-2}
0.3	1.4901×10^{-1}	1.5001×10^{-1}	1.5108×10^{-1}	1.5232×10^{-1}	1.5381×10^{-1}
0.5	1.5033×10^{-1}	1.5055×10^{-1}	1.5057×10^{-1}	1.5047×10^{-1}	1.5019×10^{-1}
0.7	1.0476×10^{-1}	1.0463×10^{-1}	1.0435×10^{-1}	1.0386×10^{-1}	1.0311×10^{-1}
0.9	3.6431×10^{-2}	3.6296×10^{-2}	3.6119×10^{-2}	3.5898×10^{-2}	3.5629×10^{-2}

6. Conclusion

This paper presents the numerical solution of fractional reaction-diffusion equations with nonlocal boundary conditions. To get the desired aim, we utilized the Lucas polynomials and their properties. In the process of the solution, we used the operational matrix of derivative. Finally, we solve a problem to demonstrate the accuracy of the approach.

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